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Research Article

**URGENT SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF NECROTISING
FASCIITIS AND ITS OUTCOME IN DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL,
DG KHAN****¹Dr Fida Hussain, ²Dr Muhammad Usman Amiruddin, ³Dr Muhammad Hafeez Ullah,
⁴Dr Rasheed Ahmad**^{1,3}FCPS General Surgery, Assistant Professor DHQ Teaching Hospital, D.G. Khan, ²FCPS Plastic Surgery, Senior Registrar DHQ Teaching Hospital, D.G. Khan, ⁴FCPS Assistant Professor Surgery, D.G. Khan Medical College and Teaching Hospital D.G. Khan.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the role of rapid and aggressive surgical debridement in reducing mortality and morbidity associated with necrotizing fasciitis and the role of bacteriology and antibiotic susceptibility as a result of this debilitating condition.

Study Design: A Retrospective Study.

Place and Duration: In the Surgical Unit 1 of DHQ Teaching Hospital, DG Khan for Two-year duration from August, 2017 to August, 2019.

Methodology: Forty patients diagnosed of Necrotising fasciitis including Fournier's gangrene were managed in this surgical unit were selected. All patients underwent emergency major debridement with broad-spectrum antibiotic treatment and regular dressing and debridement and hemodynamic support in the operating room.

Results: 43.5 years was the mean age of presentation with range 16-78 years. Many cases presented late after five days of the disease onset. In most cases predisposing causes were found. When necrotizing fasciitis was suspected, a rapid and rapid surgical approach was initiated with immediate antibiotic and major debridement in the operating room and regular small debridement in the ward and if necessary, in the operating room. Mortality was 6 in this study.

Conclusion: Early diagnosis, all necrotic tissues radical surgical debridement, forceful nutritional support and broad-spectrum antibiotics are specific treatment options for necrotizing fasciitis.

Key words: Necrotizing fasciitis, surgical debridement, intravenous antibiotics.

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INTRODUCTION:

Necrotizing fasciitis (NF) is the infection of soft tissue determined by rapid spread of inflammation and subsequent muscle fascia necrosis, subcutaneous fat and, in some cases, signs of epidermis and systemic toxicity [1]. Necrosis is generally limited to the plane of the muscle fascia and in some cases the skin can be salvaged [2]. There are two clinical categories. Necrotizing fasciitis Type I is a polymicrobial infection initiated by anaerobic and aerobic bacteria and is usually seen in patients with underlying medical or surgical problems. Type II necrotizing fasciitis denotes mono-microbial infection instigated by group A streptococci and rarely cMRSA-induced necrotizing fasciitis (defined as community-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* as a mono-microbial infection) [3]. Type II can occur in patients of any age set and deprived of complex medical conditions. Preparatory factors comprise closed trauma history, tissue hypoxia, PMLN dysfunction, liquefactive necrosis, proliferation of anaerobic bacteria, chicken pox, the use of injectable drugs, birth, injuries, surgical procedures, penetrations, exposure to a "case", and injuries such as burns [4]. The other two types of infections, which are generally penetrating accepted as necrotizing fasciitis types, are Fournier's gangrene and cervical necrotizing fasciitis. Fournier's gangrene is the uncommon and mostly causes the fulminant necrotizing fasciitis of the genital perineum and genital region normally because of synergistic polymicrobial infection. This is truly emergency situation which must be deal accordingly and typically seen in diabetic, elderly and immune-compromised patients.

Similarly, there is recurrent overlap between spontaneous gangrenous myositis and necrotizing fasciitis⁵. Early necrotizing fasciitis recognition is significant as a marked process can proceed fairly

rapidly to those related with intense systemic toxicity, tissue destruction, death or loss of limb⁶. In this case, mortality and morbidity are very high due to late delivery and late diagnosis of the disease, because in most cases the early clinical diagnosis of the necrotizing fasciitis area is difficult and can be confirmed only after intervention Surgery [7-8].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Retrospective Study was held in the Surgical Unit 1 of DHQ Teaching Hospital, DG Khan for Two-year duration from August, 2017 to August, 2019.

40 total patients were selected for the study. Most of the patients were delayed and, in most cases predisposing causes were present.

Including criteria

All patients with necrotizing fasciitis and Fournier's gangrene. The diagnosis of NF is confirmed mainly on clinical basis and by MRI and frozen section.

Exclusion Criteria

Other skin infections and Dermatological problems.

Diagnostic Criteria:

1. Sudden Onset of Pain
2. Swelling
3. Toxaemia
4. Area of Erythema (spreads quickly into the normal skin without sharp demarcation)
5. Purplish and Dusky Skin (Multiple identical patches of gangrenous skin)
6. Skin Gangrene (Bullae with fascial necrosis, local crepitus, putrid discharge.
7. MOF, fever and shock.

If the above criteria score is above six have high suspicion of NF and if it is above eight it is labelled as high risk of necrotising fasciitis.

Clinical Findings	Type 1	Type 2	Gas Gangrene	Pyomyositis	Myositis viral/ parasitic
Fever	++	++++	+++	++	++
Diffuse Pain	+	+	+	+	++++
Local Pain	++	++++	++++	++	++
Systemic Toxicity	++	++++	++++	+	+
Gas in Tissue	++	-	++++	-	-
Obvious portal of entry	++++	+	++++	-	-
DM	++++	+	-	-	-

Unexplained pain rises rapidly over time and may be the 1st necrotizing fasciitis sign. When necrotizing fasciitis is supposed, it is especially suspected in patients with micro-system-related results such as tachycardia, fever, tense edema outside the affected skin, hypotension, blisters / blisters, disproportionate pain, subcutaneous gas, crepitation and soft tissue infection. The following principles were adopted. Intravenous antibiotics containing ampicillin or ampicillin-sulbactam combined with Metronidazole were immediately initiated. Patients who were previously hospitalized or recently on antibiotics, using ticarcillin-clavulanate, piperacillin-tazobactam, fluoro-quinolone, or third-generation cephalosporin. These antibiotics were used until the results of certain cultures and the sensitivity of the organisms were present. An aggressive and comprehensive emergency debridement was performed in all necrotic tissues (subcutaneous tissues, skin and fascia) until healthy bleeding tissue was reached. With iodine, hydrogen peroxide and saline; wound was thoroughly washed. For culture and histopathological examination; excised tissues were sent. Less than 12 hours later, the wound was examined and, if necessary, additional debridement was performed. In addition to the two main OT days in the main operating room during

hospitalization, all wounds were examined regularly in the morning and afternoon rounds. Two bandages and necrosectomy were performed daily. When healthy granulation tissue appeared in the local wound dressing, the wound culture was performed with normal saline until it isolated any organism, and strict procedures for wound closure were performed. Precise procedures such as secondary closure, discrete thickness skin graft and fasciocutaneous flap were performed depending on the skin defect, patient's age and viability of the tissues. After recovery, the patients were discharged and followed up for 3-6 months.

RESULTS:

40 total patients with necrotizing fasciitis including Fournier's gangrene were admitted to our unit and were included for two years study after informed consent. The mean age of presentation was 43.5 years (range 16-78). Twenty-nine patients (72.5%) who presented late 5-6 days after the onset of symptoms had pain, fever, swelling and erythema in the affected area, and 17 patients (42.6%) had cracking. At the first examination, 9 (22.5%) patients reported a flu-like disease before the development of skin infection symptoms, while 27 (67.7%) reported fever associated with body pain.

Table I. Isolated organisms and their percentage

Organisms	No.	%
Streptococcus species	8	20
Corynebacterium	5	12.5
Staphylococcus species	7	17.5
Escherichia coli (E. coli)	9	22.5
Bacteroides species	6	15
Pseudomonas	5	12.5
Clostridium welchii	4	10
Prevotella	3	7.5
Proteus species	7	17.5
Peptostreptococcus	3	7.5
Porphyromonas species	2	5
Enterococci	7	17.5

When it comes to predisposing conditions, 5 patients after laparotomy (2 firearms), 4 patients' minor trauma, 4 patients dorsal carbide, 3 patients intra gluteal / intra deltoid injection, 2 patients snake bites, 2 patients union of skin, 2 patients psoas abscess, 2 ' appendectomy in 2 patients, limb injury in 2 patients, intravenous drug addict in 2 patients, palmer fissure in

1 patient, no cause was identified in the remaining patients. The common medical conditions seen in these cases were diabetes mellitus in 23 (57.50%) patients, chronic renal failure in 9 (22.50%), liver failure in 7 (17.5%) and tuberculosis in 5 (12.50%) patients.

Predisposing Factors	%	No. of Dedridements	Hospital Stay (Avg)	Outcome Died/Recovered	No. of Patients
Idiopathic	17.5	4	22	2/5	7
Trauma	10	4	9	0/4	4
I/M Injections	7.5	3	21	0/4	3
Boil on skin	5	3	26	0/2	2
Psoas Abscesses	5	4	17	0/2	2
Post Lapratomy	12.5	6	32	1/5	5
Carbuncle	10	4	21	0/4	4
Post append	5	3	39	0/2	2
Post ileostomy	5	5	26	0/2	2
Firearm	5	4	17	1/2	2
Palmer fissure	2.5	3	13	0/1	1
Snake bite	5	5	41	1/1	2
IV Drug Users	5	4	22	1/1	2
FA injuries to legs	5	3	29		2

Table II. Presentation and outcome of patients

These 11 (27.5%) patients had more than one of the previous conditions. All patients underwent an aggressive surgical debridement. Twenty-four hours after admission, 17 patients were operated, and 9 patients were operated within 3 to 4 days, 6 patients were delayed from patients seeking late help in the hospital, and the delay in the remaining patients was mostly slower. Antibiotics were started immediately and were taken for pus culture, and all subjects' first debridement session and antibiotic susceptibility were

changed accordingly. In our study, the cases of Fournier's gangrene were managed on urgent basis by wound excision until the healthy tissue was observed. Once the granulation tissue was formed over the wound the patients were done with skin grafting and the result were good anatomically and functionally.

The pre-operative and post-operative pictures of Fournier's gangrene after wound excision and after skin grafting are given below.

DISCUSSION:

In 1924, Melany and Cullen described an infectious process in subcutaneous tissue separately, calling it skin gangrene and synergistic gangrene, respectively [9]. The term 'necrotizing fasciitis' was introduced by Wilson in 1952. The bacteriology of the condition is highly variable and has changed over time. Years in literature. Various synergistic infections have been reported, but no specific combination has been found to be particularly relevant. In this study, we found multi-bacterial aetiology in almost all cases [10]. Bacteria can be isolated from almost all cases of necrotizing fasciitis type I. In two series from Maryland and Singapore, two-thirds had mixed aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. Type II necrotizing fasciitis causes VAS and was previously called streptococcal gangrene. In the 1990s, there was a dramatic increase in the number of invasive infections such as necrotizing fasciitis caused by GAS. Although the literature review involving five prospective studies did not show a correlation, the development of anti-nsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and necrotizing VAS infection, in this study, 12 patients had a history of NSAID use. However, it can be said that NSAIDs may mask the usual signs of inflammation, thus delaying the diagnosis. Laboratory findings are usually non-specific Blood tests usually show leukocytosis with marked left shift coagulopathy and increased studies in serum concentrations of lactate, creatine kinase a, and creatinine Several studies have been conducted on the role of intravenous immunoglobulin in neutralization [11-12]. Treatment of circulating streptococci when hypotension occurs. There appears to be little doubt that some IVIG groups contain neutralizing antibodies against certain clostridial toxins and streptococcal supernatants [13]. We could not use IVIG be Even with the best

treatment, necrotizing fasciitis is associated with significant mortality. In different studies, mortality rates are associated with mortality in 21% of patients with type I necrotizing fasciitis, 14% with type II necrotizing fasciitis, and infection in patients with streptococcal toxic shock syndrome. GAS is 22 percent in patients with cervical necrotizing fasciitis and 22 to 40 percent in patients with Fournier's gangrene [14]. Hyperbaric oxygen therapy may reduce mortality and limit Fournier's degree of debridement in gangrene and necrotizing fasciitis, but the results are conflicting. An observational study of 26 patients with Fournier's gangrene found the mortality rate significantly lower in HBO-treated patients (42% versus 7%). In a second observational study of 29 patients with necrotizing fasciitis, significantly lower debridement and a lower mortality rate (66 vs. 23 percent) were recorded when HBO was used. In contrast, a larger study of 42 patients with Fournier's gangrene showed an increase in mortality, morbidity, and cost of treatment among HBO-treated patients [15]. In this study, we do not use HBO treatment. In our 40 patient's series, 6 patients died, so our mortality was 15%.

CONCLUSION:

The key to the treatment of patients with necrotizing fasciitis is urgent aggressive surgical debridement in all necrotic tissues. Simultaneously also start intravenous fluid therapy and broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy and treat systemic diseases such as diabetes because they are widely available in Pakistan and most patients cannot afford them.

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